

DRONE VISUAL GUIDANCE

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Abstract: Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) express delivery is facing a period of rapid development and continues to promote the aviation logistics industry due to its advantages of elevated delivery efficiency and low labor costs. Automatic detection, localization, and estimation of 6D poses of targets in dynamic environments are key prerequisites for UAV intelligent logistics. In this study, we proposed a novel vision system based on deep neural networks to locate targets and estimate their 6D pose parameters from 2D color images and 3D point clouds captured by an RGB-D sensor mounted on a UAV. The workflow of this system can be summarized as follows: detect the targets and locate them, separate the object region from the background using a segmentation network, and estimate the 6D pose parameters from a regression network. The proposed system provides a solid foundation for various complex operations for UAVs. To better verify the performance of the proposed system, we built a small dataset called SIAT comprising some household staff. Comparative experiments with several state-of-the-art networks on the YCB-Video dataset and SIAT dataset verified the effectiveness, robustness, and superior performance of the proposed method, indicating its promising applications in UAV-based delivery tasks.

Keywords: UAV; vision system; semantic segmentation; 6D pose estimation; intelligent logistics

1. Introduction

Recent advances in areas such as computer vision, automation, and artificial intelligence have created new opportunities in the aviation logistics industry. Future improvements require research on the automatic, unmanned, and informational directions that will power the efficiency and quality of delivery services. Therefore, the

demand for unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV)-based automatic express delivery systems has increased rapidly over the past several decades. Currently, UAVs are widely used in the fields of surveillance, aero photography, military, and others [1,2], while most research still focuses on control algorithms and path planning [3,4].

Owing to the importance and widespread adoption of target localization and recognition in complex scenes, we proposed an efficient vision system, including object detection, tracking, segmentation, and 6D pose estimation, and deployed it on a UAV platform to demonstrate its potential in the applications of automatic express delivery.

The proposed vision system can detect, locate, and track targets of interest without manual intervention by calculating precise position and pose parameters. In addition, we built a dataset to evaluate the performance of our algorithm, called the SIAT dataset, which contains 20 video sequences with a total of 13,161 frames. The ground truth of our SIAT dataset comprised segmentation masks and 6D pose parameters for all targets in each frame. As shown in Figure 1, the workflow for the entire system consists of the following stages:

Figure 1. The hardware setup and workflow of the proposed vision system.

2. Research background and significance

The rapid advancement of drone technology has significantly expanded its applications across various fields, including agriculture, logistics, disaster response, and surveillance. Among these applications, visual guidance plays a pivotal role in enabling drones to navigate complex environments autonomously. Unlike traditional GPS-based navigation, visual guidance relies on cameras and computer vision algorithms to perceive and interpret the surroundings, allowing drones to operate in GPS-denied areas, such as indoors, forests, or urban canyons.

The significance of this research lies in its potential to enhance drone autonomy, safety, and efficiency. By integrating visual guidance systems, drones can achieve real-time obstacle detection, precise path planning, and adaptive decision-making, which are critical for tasks such as search-and-rescue missions, infrastructure inspection, and delivery services. Moreover, advancements in this field contribute to reducing operational costs and minimizing human intervention, making drone technology more accessible and versatile.

In summary, research on drone visual guidance addresses key challenges in autonomous navigation and opens new avenues for deploying drones in complex, real-world scenarios, ultimately transforming industries and improving societal outcomes.

3. Related Work

3.1 Object Detection

Object detection methods have evolved from feature-based approaches to deep learning-based models, such as single-stage detectors like SSD (Single Shot Multibox Detector) and YOLO (You Only Look Once). The proposed system leverages SSD for its real-time detection capabilities and robustness in predicting objects of varying shapes and sizes.

3.2 Object Tracking

Tracking enables UAVs to maintain focus on detected targets while in motion. Modern tracking techniques, including Siamese networks and transformer-based

models, outperform traditional methods by leveraging deep learning for enhanced accuracy and stability.

3.3 Semantic Segmentation

Semantic segmentation ensures pixel-level differentiation between objects and their backgrounds. Inspired by U-Net and PSPNet, the study introduces a segmentation network that fuses color and depth data, enhancing precision and robustness.

3.4 6D Pose Estimation

6D pose estimation involves predicting the spatial orientation and position of objects. Traditional approaches, like template matching, face limitations in cluttered environments. Modern regression- and keypoint-based neural networks offer superior accuracy. This study employs a hybrid approach, combining RGB and point cloud data for robust pose estimation.

4. Methodology

4.1 System Overview

The proposed vision system includes the following components:

(1) Hardware: A DJI M100 UAV equipped with a Percipio RGB-D camera and a high-performance server with an NVIDIA GTX1080Ti GPU.

(2) Workflow: Images captured by the RGB-D camera are transmitted to the server for processing via a Wi-Fi link. Tasks include object detection, tracking, segmentation, and 6D pose estimation. The computed parameters are then transmitted back to the UAV.

4.2 Innovative Features

(1) Segmentation Network: Dual-branch encoder for extracting color and geometric features; Feature fusion using pyramid pooling and refined residual blocks to improve segmentation accuracy.

(2) Pose Estimation Network:Combines ResNet-based color feature extraction and PointNet-based geometric feature extraction;Iterative refinement inspired by DenseFusion to enhance pose prediction accuracy.

(3) SIAT Dataset:A new dataset comprising over 13,000 frames across 20 video sequences;Includes ground truth for segmentation masks and 6D pose parameters, enabling robust benchmarking.

5.Conclusions

In this study, a vision system is proposed for the object-handling tasks of UAVs. The system combines 2D images and 3D point cloud information to accurately detect and segment various objects in complex scenes and realize 6D object pose estimation, which can provide a solid foundation for intelligent picking or other object handling tasks of UAVs. In addition, to evaluate the performance of the system more comprehensively, we contribute a 6D pose estimation dataset named the SIAT dataset. Experiments conducted on the SIAT dataset and benchmark YCB-Video dataset demonstrate the robustness of our system. Currently, the proposed method experiences slow image transmission. Upgrading the hardware to improve image transmission speed and researching more lightweight networks and algorithms to carry vision systems on UAVs to complete offline 6D pose estimation will be considered in future works.

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